

Dilemmas in open scholarly communication

- Brief, hypothetical (though practice-based) situations
- Written from researcher's perspective
- Exercise: What would you do? And what would you advise the researcher to do?
- Explicate underlying values:
 - a) the researcher's, as provided in the text
 - b) yours! From professional position – and personal perspective?
 - c) which tensions may arise? Which stakeholders are involved?
- How would the dilemma change if the researcher were in a different career stage? At a different institution? In another research field?